

FOOD CONSUMPTION PATTERN AMONG STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY OF ADEYEMI COLLEGE OF EDUCATION ONDO

Mrs. C. A. Olarewaju

Department of Home Economics, Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo

Abstract

This study set out to determine the feeding habits of male and female students in Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo. One hundred and twenty students (sixty males and sixty females) of the College were randomly selected. Questionnaire was used for data collection. Frequency counts and percentages were the main statistical tools used for analysis.

Result showed that majority (71.67%) of the male and female respondents eat thrice a day. Most students (68.33% male and 98.33% female) cook their food personally. Majority (63.33% of male and 76.67% of female) claimed they eat fruits and vegetables once a day. 40.00% of each group consumed the fruits and vegetables after meals. Taboos had little influence on the food consumption patterns. More female mixed meals than the male students. Time and money factors ranked highest among the reasons for missing meals. Male students received more feeding allowances than the female ones. Students' parents were mostly civil servants and business men and women. Most students preferred Rice and Eba as their staple food. Recommendation for improving feeding habits include encouraging students to include proteinous food e.g beans in their diet was made.

Introduction

Food habits and their role in nutrition

According to William Eaton et al (2004) "eating is one of life's most pleasurable activities". Food choices affect the diet quality of individuals and the type of crops that people grow. All people have their likes, dislikes and beliefs about food. Europeans may think it is disgusting that some Chinese eat dogs and some Africans eat insects. Africans dislike the raw oysters and eels eaten by many English men. The Chinese believe that the French's habit of eating snails and frogs' legs is horrible. The Russians' great delicacy is caviar, the small oily black eggs of fish. Scotsmen like to eat haggis (stomach of a sheep filled with cat meal and chopped liver)

Eaton et al 2004 also stated that most people are conservative in their food habits. They tend to like what their mothers cooked for them when they were young and what was served to them at school. The foods that people ate without a second thought in childhood are seldom revolting to them in later life. He observed that individuals are further influenced by friends, what those around them eat and foods thought to be sophisticated, expensive or are popularly considered good for health. There is a dislike of being conspicuous or different from others in the society with regard to food eaten.

He also added that food habits differ most widely in regard to foods of animal origin. Few people have strong feelings about cereals or roots, vegetables or fruits. The affected foods are therefore usually those rich in protein. Because protein is deficient in many African diets, encouragement not discouragement should be given to the consumption of any food of animal origin irrespective of how bizarre they may seem. The sophisticated or educated man is doing a disservice to his community if after his life in the city, he returns to his village and tells his family that it is disgusting to eat lake flies or locusts, cats or cannies. Instead any person who has a liking for some of those unusual protein rich foods is doing a service to his country if he persuades others to try them.

Some good traditional food habits

Simoncropton (2004) is of the opinion that the habit of eating protein rich foods such as insects, snakes, baboons, mongooses, dogs, cats, peculiar sea creatures, snails and so on is very definitely beneficial. He also pointed out that the traditional use of certain wild green leaves such as sesame is another habit which is of real benefit. Those dark green leaves are rich sources of carotene, ascorbic acid, iron and calcium,

they contain useful quantities of protein and it is highly desirable that rural people continue to eat them. The traditional dark green leaves such as amaranth and also those from cultivated food crops such as pumpkin, sweet potato and cassava plants are very much richer than the pale leafy European vegetable such as cabbage and lettuce.

He noted that the traditional method of grain preparation produce a more nutritious product than does elaborate machine milling. The sprouting of legumes which is practiced in some communities prior to cooking enhance their nutritive value. This also applies to the soaking of whole grain cereals. This is done before making local beans (Pombe) and some alcoholic beverages (e.g togwa). All these usually have a high vitamin B content.

Bassey and Umar (2000) emphasized that many of the bad taboos which existed in Africa a quarter of a century ago have already disappeared or are rapidly doing so, as a result of education, mixing of tribal groups wide exposure. Also a feeling of nationhood replacing tribalism in the newly independent states. It is better for influential local people to try to change nutritionally bad habits if it is considered probable that the health of the community will thus be improved.

Statement of Problem

The problem of inadequate nutrition i.e too much or too little nutrient intake to the detriment of the others have a great influence on the individual. Food consumption pattern of some people are limited by taboos and other cultural and religious practices. Also economic hardship can lead people to consume foods that are cheap as well as bulky (quantity) rather than its quality. Time and money (income) also influence food consumption pattern of people. Individuals are also influenced by friends, by what those around them eat and by what foods are thought to be sophisticated expensive or are popularly considered good for health. It is in the light of this that the study sets out to investigate the feeding habit of students.

Objectives

The objectives of this study are to find out

- (1) The food consumption pattern of students in Adeyemi College of Education
 - (a) the number of times they eat.
 - (b) students' sources of meals.
 - (c) snacks, fruits and vegetable consumption pattern.
 - (d) if students have food taboos and the effect on their food consumption pattern.
 - (e) if students missed meals and their reasons for doing so.
 - (f) foods preferred by students (if any).
- (2) Feeding allowances collected by students from parents monthly.
- (3) Students' parents occupation and effect on their food consumption pattern.

Methodology

Food consumption survey was conducted among students of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo.

Source of Data

The data was collected from one hundred and twenty students of different habitations, different socio-economic groups, age and status, living on campus, rented apartments outside the school and with their parents.

Sampling size and Technique

One hundred and twenty students (sixty males and sixty females were randomly chosen to respond to the questionnaires.

Data Collection Instrument

The instrument used for the data collection was a questionnaire schedule which sought information on where students obtained their meals, whether they missed meals and reasons for doing so, type of staple foods frequently consumed, snacks, fruits and vegetables consumption pattern, types of foods avoided and reason for such avoidance, their beliefs and taboos, feeding allowance collected per month, parents occupation and food preference.

Data analysis

Frequency counts and percentages, were used to analyse the data.

Table I: Distribution of respondents according to number of times they eat daily**Male**

Variables	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartments		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Once	0	0.00	0	0.0	0	0.00	0	0.00
Twice	5	8.33	0	0.0	3	5.00	8	13.33
Thrice	20	33.33	10	16.7	13	21.67	43	71.67
More than thrice	5	8.33	0	0.0	4	6.67	9	15.00
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100

Female

	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Once	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Twice	6	10.00	2	3.33	4	10.02	14	23.33
Thrice	22	36.67	7	11.67	14	23.33	43	71.67
More than thrice	2	3.33	1	1.67	0	0.00	3	5.00
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100

Table 1 shows the number of times respondents eat in a day. None of the students both male and female eat once in a day. Majority (71.67%) eat thrice a day. Since the students eat thrice daily they have good feeding habit. The habit of eating twice may be due to lack of time or lack of food. This habit is however nutritionally bad because students need food to give them required calories for the days work.

Table 2: Students' sources of meals**Male**

	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartments		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Canteen	10	16.7	0	0.00	3	5.00	13	21.67
Food vendor	5	8.33	0	0.0	1	1.67	6	10.00
Personal preparation	15	25.00	10	16.7	16	26.67	41	68.33
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100

Female

	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Canteen	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.00	0	0.00
Food vendor	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	1.67	1	1.67
Personal preparation	30	50.0	10	16.7	19	31.67	59	98.33
Total	30	50.0	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100

Table 2 shows that the highest percentage of female students (98.33%) cooked their food personally. This could be due to the fact that females have more skills to cook than males. Also cooking is more of a feminine job than a masculine one. Students of Adeyemi College of Education prefer to cook their food themselves than to buy from food vendors or canteens. Foods cooked personally should be more hygienic and therefore safer for students to consume than foods bought from canteens or food vendors.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents according to fruits and vegetable consumption

Male								
Variables	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartments		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Once	15	25.00	10	16.7	13	21.67	38	63.33
Twice	7	11.67	0	0.0	3	5.00	10	16.7
Thrice	7	11.67	0	0.0	2	5.00	9	15.00
More than thrice	1	1.67	0	0.0	2	3.33	3	5.00
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100.00

Female								
Once	25	41.67	8	13.33	13	21.67	46	76.67
Twice	4	6.67	2	3.33	5	8.33	11	18.33
Thrice	1	1.67	0	0.00	1	1.67	2	3.33
More than thrice	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	1.67	1	1.67
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100.00

Majority of the respondents 63.33% of the male and 76.67% of the female eat fruits and vegetables once a day. This is a good feeding habit but can still be improved upon.

Table 4: Ways of Consuming Fruits

Male								
Variables	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartments		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
With meals	13	21.67	1	1.67	6	10.00	20	33.3
After meal	12	20.00	5	8.33	7	11.67	24	40.00
As snacks	5	8.33	4	6.66	7	11.67	16	26.67
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100.00

Female								
With meals	10	16.7	4	6.66	2	3.33	16	26.67
After meals	11	18.33	4	6.66	9	15.00	24	40.00
As snacks	9	15.00	2	3.33	9	15.00	20	33.3
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100.00

Table 4 shows the different forms in which the fruits and vegetables were consumed. The highest percentage of respondents (both males and females) consume fruits and vegetable after meals. The best way of consuming fruits according to Shils et al (2005) is with meals.

Table 5: Food Taboos

Variables	Male							
	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartments		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Yes	7	11.67	4	6.66	2	3.33	13	21.67
No	23	38.33	6	10.00	18	30.00	47	78.33
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100.00

Variables	Female							
	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartments		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Yes	9	15.00	2	3.33	0	0.0	11	18.33
No	21	35.00	8	13.33	20	33.3	49	81.67
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100.00

Table 5 shows that majority of the male (78.33%) and female (81.67%) respondents had no food taboos. None of the female respondents that lived in rented apartments had food taboos. It can be deduced from this table that taboos have little influence on the food consumption pattern of the students in Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo.

Table 6: Frequency distribution of Students who missed meals

Variables	Male							
	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartments		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Yes	10	16.7	0	0.0	5	8.33	15	25.00
No	20	33.3	10	16.7	15	25.00	45	75.00
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100.00

Variables	Female							
	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartments		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Yes	14	23.33	8	13.33	12	20.00	34	56.67
No	16	26.67	2	3.33	8	13.33	26	43.33
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100.00

This table shows that 56.67% of the female and 25% of the male students missed meals. More female respondents missed meals than the males, this could be due to the fact that they wanted to reduce their weight. If the practice of missing meals should continue for a long time, then individual can be exposed to the risk of stomach ulcer.

Table 7: Reasons for missing meals

Reasons	Male							
	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartment		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Money factor	4	26.7	0	0.0	2	13.3	6	40.0
Time factor	4	26.7	0	0.0	2	13.3	6	40.0
Fasting and praying	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Lack of food	2	13.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	13.3
Weight reduction	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	6.67	1	6.67
Total	10	66.7	0	0.0	5	33.20	15	100.00

Reasons	Female							
	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartment		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Money factor	4	13.33	0	0.00	2	6.67	6	20.00
Time factor	5	16.7	3	10.00	4	13.33	12	40.00
Fasting and praying	0	0.0	0	0.00	3	10.00	3	10.00
Lack of food	2	6.67	1	3.33	1	3.33	4	13.33
Weight reduction	3	10.00	0	0.00	2	6.67	5	16.70
Total	14	46.07	4	13.33	12	40.00	30	100.00

It can be seen from this table that time and money factors took the highest percentage of the reason for missing meals. For those that missed meals because of time this could be so because some students wake up late and rush for lectures thereby skipping breakfast. The practice of missing meals for weight reduction should be discouraged, instead exercise should be used.

Table 8: Distribution of respondents according to feeding allowance collected per month

Reasons	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartment		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
N1,000.00 to N1,200.00	6	10.00	7	11.67	1	1.67	14	23.33
N1,300.00 to N1,700.00	5	8.33	3	5.00	7	11.67	15	25.00
N1,800.00 to N2,500.00	13	21.67	0	0.00	6	10.00	19	31.67
N3,000.00 and above	6	10.00	0	0.00	6	10.00	12	20.00
Total	30	50.00	10	16.70	20	33.30	60	100.00

Female

N1,000.00 to N1,200.00	11	18.33	6	10.00	6	10.00	23	38.33
N1,300.00 to N1,700.00	7	11.67	4	6.67	5	8.33	16	26.67
N1,800.00 to N2,500.00	10	16.70	0	0.00	3	5.00	13	21.67
N3,000.00 and above	2	3.33	0	0.00	6	10.00	8	13.33
Total	30	50.00	10	16.70	20	33.30	60	100.00

Table 8 shows that male students were given more allowances than female students. This may be the reasons why some female students in Adeyemi College of Education look for other ways of getting money. The highest percentage of male respondents (31.67) were given between one thousand and eight hundred and two thousand and five hundred Naira as feeding allowance per month. The highest percentage of female respondents (38.33) were given between one thousand and one thousand and two hundred Naira. This shows that the male students received more feeding allowance than the female ones.

Table 9: Distribution of respondents according to their parents occupation

Male

Reasons	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartment		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Petty trading	5	8.33	1	1.67	2	3.33	8	13.33
Civil servant	8	13.33	4	6.67	8	13.3	20	33.3
Teaching	6	10.00	2	3.33	3	5.00	11	18.33
Business	8	13.33	1	1.67	4	6.67	13	21.67
Others (specify)	3	5.00	2	3.33	3	5.00	8	13.33
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100.00

Female

Petty trading	9	15.00	1	1.67	5	8.33	15	25.00
Civil servant	5	8.33	4	6.66	2	3.33	11	18.33
Teaching	5	8.33	3	5.00	5	8.33	13	21.67
Business	9	15.00	2	3.33	7	11.67	18	30.00
Others (specify)	2	3.33	0	0.00	1	1.67	3	5.00
Total	30	50.00	10	16.70	20	33.3	60	100.00

33.3% of the male respondents indicated that their parents were civil servants while 30% of female respondents indicated that theirs were business men and women. The parent's occupation and income may determine the amount of money given to students as feeding allowance.

Table 10: Food Preference

Male

Reasons	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartment		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Rice	7	11.67	4	6.66	7	11.67	18	30.00
Eba	8	13.33	1	1.67	3	5.00	12	20.00
Beans	2	3.33	1	1.67	0	0.00	3	5.00
Yam	5	8.33	0	0.00	1	1.67	6	10.00
Pounded yam	1	1.67	1	1.67	1	1.67	3	5.00
Fufu	0	0.00	1	1.67	1	6.67	2	3.33
Dodo	2	3.33	0	0.00	4	6.66	6	10.00
Bread	2	3.33	0	0.00	2	3.33	4	6.66
Pap	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Amala	3	5.00	1	1.67	1	1.67	5	8.33
Gari	0	0.00	1	1.67	0	0.00	1	1.67
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100.00

Female

Rice	7	11.67	6	10.00	9	15.00	22	36.67
Eba	8	13.33	1	1.67	2	3.33	11	18.33
Beans	2	3.33	2	3.33	4	6.66	8	13.33
Yam	4	6.66	1	1.67	0	0.00	5	8.33
Pounded yam	1	1.67	0	0.00	1	1.67	2	3.33
Fufu	2	3.33	0	0.00	0	1.67	2	3.33
Dodo	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	1.67	1	1.67
Bread	5	8.33	0	0.00	3	5.00	8	13.33
Pap	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Amala	1	1.67	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	1.67
Gari	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	30	50.00	10	16.70	20	33.3	60	100.00

Table 10 shows that the highest percentage of respondents both male (30 and 20) and female (36.67 and 18.33) indicated Rice and Eba (respectively) as their staple food. i.e. the food they frequently consume. The least preferred were Pap and Gaari. This could be due to the fact that rice and Eba are easy to prepare and can be cooked within a short time.

Table 11: Distribution of respondents according to snacks consumption.

Reasons	Living on campus		Living with parents		Living in rented apartment		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
	Yes	21	35.00	10	16.7	13	21.67	44
No	9	15.00	0	0.0	7	11.67	16	25.67
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.30	60	100.00

Female

Yes	18	30.00	8	13.33	15	25.00	41	68.33
No	12	20.00	2	3.33	5	8.33	19	31.67
Total	30	50.00	10	16.7	20	33.3	60	100.00

Table 11 shows that 73.33% of the male and 68.33% of the female respondents eat snacks between meals. The lower percentage of snacks consumption among the females may be as discussed under table 2 (i.e they have more skills to cook than males). The high percentage in the two may be due to the fact that there is no time to prepare food.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study revealed that

- (1) Majority of the students eat thrice a day. None of the students ate once a day.
- (2) Majority of the students prepared their food themselves.
- (3) Most of the students eat fruits and vegetables once a day.
- (4) Most of the students have no food taboo.
- (5) Fewer male students missed meals than the female students.
- (6) Time and money factors ranked highest among reasons for missing meals.
- (7) Male students received more feeding allowance than the female ones.
- (8) Students' parents were civil servants, businessmen and women.
- (9) Students preferred rice and eba to other foods.

Students have a good feeding habit, they should however be encouraged to consume fruits and vegetables with meals (according to Shils et al 2005) female student should involve in exercises than missing meals to reduce weight. Parents should endeavour to give their children especially the female ones more money for food so that they don't indulge in immoral acts. Government should increase the bursary award to students to help alleviate their problems. Students should be encouraged to increase their intake of proteinous foods.